

From Play to Policy: DataSenses for Inclusive Societal Engagement and Living Lab Culture

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Abstract

DataSenses is a Living Lab tool and card-based serious game - a replicable, adaptive, and empowering system that fosters co-creation, open innovation, and collaborative learning. AI-enhanced and rooted in Living Lab principles, DataSenses activates data and digital literacy, critical thinking, and collaboration for real world problem-solving.

Each deck is co-created with facilitators or educators, tailored to their audience's level and objectives, while maintaining a shared framework for measurement and benchmarking. Participants engage in problem-solving and prototyping activities ranging from personal data exploration to ecosystem-level challenges. The result is deeper analytical and critical capabilities, a shift in mindset toward shared responsibility, evidence-informed action, and inclusive understanding.

The toolkit has been deployed with university students in public governance and digital media, with managers and entrepreneurs across industries, and we plan piloting DataSenses Kids in five schools (grades 0–1) with varied cultural and pedagogical models for a period of 35 weeks and measuring the impact.

Key words

Data literacy, AI in education, Living Labs, co-creation, adaptive learning, serious games

Problem Statement

Across educational and organizational settings, data literacy remains fragmented, often limited to narrow technical skills. Learners of all ages struggle to engage with data in meaningful, context-relevant ways. Existing tools rarely offer the flexibility to adapt through co-creation or align with systematic, measurable learning frameworks. At the same time, educators and facilitators lack engaging, adaptive resources that are both rigorous and easy to use, creating a gap in delivering impactful, inclusive data learning experiences.

Methods/Approach

DataSenses is a flexible, card-based learning system built around six card types (Scenario, Role, Concept, Challenge, Action, and Reflection). Each deck is co-designed with educators or facilitators to suit the players' age, domain, and learning goals related to evidence-informed decision-making. An AI-supported backend adapts content complexity, language, and format for each group while preserving a unified structure for measuring outcomes and enabling cross-group comparison.

Applications to date include:

- **DataSenses E-Governance** tested with public administration advanced undergraduate students for digital public services and policy co-design.
- **DataSenses Digital Media** tested with digital media master's students for digital media entrepreneurship, product development, and marketing.
- **DataSenses Leadership** tested with managers and entrepreneurs from across the country for ecosystemic thinking, change management, and business strategy.

DataSenses Kids is in development (ages 6–7), a 35-week program with five thematic modules: Self, Nature, Health, Community, and World, aligned with national math and science curricula and adaptable across subjects. The 2025–2026 pilot is planned to run in five culturally diverse schools (Romanian, German, Dutch, Norwegian and American school systems), both public and private.

The system progresses through six levels (Explorer, Reader, Maker, Thinker, Connector, Leader), evolving from analogue activities to advanced digital skills. Its structured, harmonized design will allow for benchmarking across contexts, sectors, and organizations.

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Results/Outcomes

Learning paths are personalized and measurable, leading to creative and impactful results. Participants consistently report increased clarity, confidence, and engagement with data, along with improved empathy and the ability to generate innovative solutions that alone could not have been achieved. Key outcomes include collaboratively created artefacts, such as maps, storyboards, strategic prototypes, based on both quantitative and qualitative data, research and documentation methods.

With ongoing use in both formal and non-formal educational and professional training settings, DataSenses proves the value of co-designed, adaptive learning tools in building a shared culture of inclusive, evidence-informed and creative decision-making, transforming how children and professionals alike participate in collaborative problem-solving and are able to innovate.

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